

Impact of Cache Coherence on the Performance of Shared-Memory based MPI Primitives: A Case Study for Broadcast on Intel Xeon Scalable Processors

George Katevenis
Institute of Computer Science (ICS),
Foundation for Research and
Technology – Hellas (FORTH)
Heraklion, Greece
gkatev@ics.forth.gr

Manolis Ploumidis
Institute of Computer Science (ICS),
Foundation for Research and
Technology – Hellas (FORTH)
Heraklion, Greece
ploumid@ics.forth.gr

Manolis Marazakis
Institute of Computer Science (ICS),
Foundation for Research and
Technology – Hellas (FORTH)
Heraklion, Greece
maraz@ics.forth.gr

ABSTRACT

Recent processor advances have made feasible HPC nodes with high core counts, capable of hosting tens or even, hundreds of processes. Therefore, designing MPI collective operations at the intra-node level has received significant attention over the past years. Deriving efficient algorithms for modern HPC nodes, with complex internal topologies and memory hierarchies, is challenging. Moreover, the cache coherency protocol, and its impact on performance, further complicate algorithm design for MPI collectives. This latter concern is often only partially addressed.

In this work, we demonstrate a particularly challenging performance degradation scenario in the case of shared-memory-based MPI broadcast, on three generations of the Intel Xeon Scalable processor architecture. Based on analysis of hardware-based performance counters, we conclude that the performance degradation observed is attributed to the cache coherency protocol and the multi-socket configuration of the execution platforms examined. We present a number of novel approaches designed to amend this effect, and apply them in a cache coherency aware version of the MPI broadcast implementation. We reduce the overall latency of the broadcast operation by up to 1.5× and 1.25× for small and large messages, respectively.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Theory of computation** → **Parallel computing models**;
Shared memory algorithms.

KEYWORDS

HPC, MPI, intra-node, cache coherence protocol

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1 INTRODUCTION

Although entering its fourth decade, Message Passing Interface (MPI) [6] remains the dominant standard for exploiting available parallelism and resources in modern HPC systems. MPI offers collective operations, which allow communication between groups of processes. A huge amount of effort has been put on optimizing these operations, on a wide range of different contexts. Examples include algorithms with improved performance and tuning capabilities [34], or hierarchical and topology-aware ones [2, 7, 24]. Several approaches optimize performance by leveraging special features of interconnects, such as RDMA [2, 36] and hardware-assisted acceleration of primitives such as reductions [1].

Recent processor advances have led to nodes with high core counts, multi-level memory hierarchies and complex internal topologies. Such nodes are able to host tens to hundreds of processes. As a result, deriving high performance implementations for collectives at the intra-node level is challenging, and thus has received significant attention over the years. Key parameters that affect the performance of MPI collectives at the intra-node level are node topology-awareness, copy scheme (shared-memory-based or kernel-assisted single-copy) and type of implementation (direct or layered over point-to-point messages). Several approaches infer and utilize information about the node's topology [9, 26]. Their goal is to bridge the mismatch between the node's physical topology and the virtual topology implied by the corresponding primitive's communication pattern. Such a mismatch can result in increased traffic over distant and expensive links, and increased contention due to fan-in or fan-out patterns. In regard to the copy scheme employed, a notable number of approaches rely on the shared memory segment approach [3, 18]. This scheme requires two copies – one for placing the data in the shared memory segment, and a second one for the receiving processes to copy it out. However, these copies have several side-effects on performance. For one, they incur increased overhead and heightened CPU load. Additionally, a less obvious effect, is that they create cache pollution, which can cause eviction of application data [3]. To mitigate these side effects, several studies have leveraged kernel-assisted single-copy mechanisms [12, 13, 25, 26], most commonly though CMA [37], KNEM [3] or XPMEM [38].

Another parameter that affects the performance of MPI collectives at the intra-node level is caching effects. Several studies have introduced some form of cache awareness in their implementations. The most common issues addressed are avoidance of false sharing;

Figure 1: MPI broadcast latency for various message sizes, number of ranks, and platforms

packing both control and actual data in a single cache line; avoiding cache pollution, which results in evicted application data; and increasing the amount of data transferred via shared caches, which reduces latency and saves memory bandwidth. However, the cache coherence protocol itself also affects performance.

Several works study the impact of the cache coherence protocol. Authors in [27] show that the HPL and DGEMM benchmarks may occasionally suffer performance degradation due to L2 misses, attributed to evictions caused by snoop filter conflicts (the purpose and functionality of snoop filters are discussed in Section 2.3). In [5], the authors discuss a common sharing pattern, where multiple processors alternate accesses for read and subsequent writes on a shared datum. They present adaptive coherence protocols to handle such *migratory* data and reduce access overhead. Work in [15] exposes the overhead incurred when accessing data whose coherence state is in distant tiles. They suggest alternatives for core-to-core & core-to-CHA affinity, and thread-to-core scheduling (where CHA is the caching & home agent, discussed in Section 2.2). In [4] the authors explore the effect of different work scheduling and data allocation approaches on cache coherence traffic for the *bullion S* system. Several studies devise sophisticated benchmarks and models for memory & cache latency and bandwidth [11, 30, 35]. They take into account data locality (e.g. shared cache, foreign NUMA, remote socket), contention & congestion, as well as different MESIF or MOESI cache line states. In the context of MPI, the work in [32, 33] leverages such sophisticated models to derive optimized implementations for MPI primitives.

In contrast to the aforementioned studies, in this work, we focus on a performance anomaly phenomenon that arises in multi-socket node configurations of the more recent Intel Xeon Scalable processor architecture. We analyze the cache coherence protocol of the architecture, identify the root cause for the phenomenon, and discuss software techniques to address it.

1.1 Motivation

In this work, we study a framework that implements intra-node MPI collectives over shared memory (directly, without relying on point-to-point messages). This framework is part of our previous research work, and its design, implementation, and evaluation are available in [20]. The framework utilizes both shared memory segment communication, and XPMEM’s single-copy capabilities, for

small and larger messages, respectively. Synchronization is implemented explicitly, following the single-writer paradigm, where one process acts as the owner of a datum or flag, while one or more other processes access it in read-only mode. Finally, it implements collective operations with various communication patterns. In this paper, we focus on a topology-agnostic flat tree.

In Figure 1, we evaluate the performance of the shared-memory broadcast offered by the framework, on two dual-socket nodes based on the Cascade Lake and Ice Lake server processor architectures, part of the Intel Xeon Scalable family. We use the MPI broadcast benchmark from the OSU micro-benchmark suite [23] (version 7.0). In accordance with our prior findings in [20], we modify the benchmark to alter the transmitted data before each iteration, in order to avoid caching effects. Both nodes contain 24 cores per CPU socket, for a total of 48 cores in the system. Figure 1a plots the latency of the operation, using a message size of 1 KB, for increasingly higher numbers of participating ranks. The plotted latency is the average of 30 runs of the benchmark, while the shaded area around the line illustrates the standard deviation of the runs. When 24 or less ranks are present, only the first socket is populated, while for 25 or more total ranks, the second socket starts getting occupied as well. During our evaluation, we come across a characteristic and unexpected result; the average latency rises sharply and very significantly, when even a single rank is placed on the remote socket. Figures 1b and 1c similarly plot the broadcast latency, across multiple message sizes, on the Cascade Lake and Ice Lake nodes, respectively. The observed performance degradation, when ranks in a second socket are introduced, appears to be coherent across all message sizes, and is present on both architecture generations, though it’s less pronounced on Ice Lake. We investigate this effect, analyze and discover the cause for it, and develop techniques to amend it.

1.2 Contributions

We explore the effect of the cache coherence protocol on the performance of a shared-memory-based broadcast. We make the following key contributions:

- We identify a characteristic performance anomaly in shared-memory broadcast, in multi-socket configurations of nodes based on the Intel Xeon Scalable architecture. We show that the phenomenon is coherent across the three different generations of the architecture.

- We outline how the cache coherency protocol of the processors operates during shared-memory communication.
- We analyze the identified phenomenon, and show that it is caused by the cache coherency scheme. We explain the differences in the way it exhibits itself across the three architectural generations.
- We develop a number of novel approaches designed to counteract the effect, and demonstrate their ability to improve operation performance. Our techniques consider two key aspects: (i) ordering of accesses by processes on different sockets; (ii) using different shared buffers and synchronization structures for local and remote accesses. These techniques accelerate large- and small- sized accesses, respectively.
- We produce a cache-coherency-aware version of MPI broadcast, that mitigates the phenomenon and reduces the overall latency of the shared-memory broadcast, by up to 1.5× and 1.25× for small and large messages, respectively.

We expect the identified phenomenon to be significant for any shared-memory-based communication algorithm, including other similar MPI primitives. Furthermore, we expect it to be relevant for multiple other multi-socket platforms, where a cache line can migrate to a foreign cache as a result of a cross-socket access. Prominent examples of such platforms are those with MESI-, MESIF-, or MOESI-based cache coherency-protocols, where processes in remote domains may acquire cache lines in the exclusive state.

2 BACKGROUND

In this section, we provide information on the platforms used in this study, and the shared-memory broadcast algorithm that we examine. Furthermore, we offer a brief description of various mechanisms, related to the cache coherency protocol of the processors.

2.1 Software stack

As discussed in Section 1.1, the framework studied in this work implements MPI collectives over shared-memory. The framework is realized as a component in OpenMPI, and in the context of this work, implements the broadcast algorithm according to a flat communication tree. Figure 2 shows the different algorithm phases. In the first step, and in the case that shared memory segment communication is used, the root rank places the data to be broadcast in an internal shared buffer. If instead the single-copy method is utilized, child processes will copy the data directly from the root’s application buffer, so such a step does not take place. In the second phase, the root sets a shared-memory resident flag, which signals child processes that the data is ready to be copied. Child processes then copy-out the data (step 3), either from the internal shared memory segment, or from the root’s buffer using XPMEM. Finally, in step 4, children acknowledge data reception, by setting another shared flag. The root polls the children’s flags, and declares the operation complete once all of them are set. For the rest of this work, we build upon this simple broadcast implementation, and use it to analyze the performance anomaly phenomenon of interest.

2.2 System description

In Table 1, we list the systems considered in this work, including details about their internal topology, and software stack components.

Figure 2: Shared-memory broadcast

Table 1: Target systems

Codename	SKX-24	CSX-48	ICX-48
Processor	2x Intel Xeon 6146	2x Intel Xeon 8260M	2x Intel Xeon 5318Y
μ arch	Skylake	Cascade Lake	Ice Lake
CPU sockets	2	2	2
NUMA domains	2	2	2
SNC mode	OFF	OFF	OFF
Cores per socket	12	24	24
Total cores	24	48	48
L1, L2 cache	1088 KB	1088 KB	1360 KB
LLC/L3 cache	25 MB	36 MB	36 MB
Linux Kernel	4.18	4.18	5.4.0
GCC	11.2.0	11.2.0	9.4.0
OpenMPI	5.0.0rc10	5.0.0rc10	5.0.0rc10

The first node, codenamed *SKX-24*, is equipped with Intel Xeon Gold processors of the Skylake micro-architecture. Nodes *CSX-48* and *ICX-48* feature 2nd and 3rd generation Xeon scalable processors, based on the the Cascade Lake and Ice Lake micro-architectures, respectively. All cores have their own private L1 and L2 caches, while all cores in each socket share a large, non-inclusive, last-level cache (LLC). An important factor across the three systems, is that they all feature multiple sockets (two) and have relatively high core counts. Internally, the processor is organized in the form of a 2D mesh [16]. Most tiles in the mesh encapsulate a core, the core’s private L1 and L2 caches, a caching & home agent (CHA), and a slice of the distributed LLC and snoop filter. Furthermore, there are tiles housing the integrated memory controllers (IMC), interfaces to the Intel Ultra Path Interconnect (UPI) links, and other auxiliary connections. The CHAs track the different copies of each cache line inside the socket, and assist in keeping them coherent. Furthermore, they are responsible for interacting with the main memory when necessary, and service all requests for cache lines that cores require but are not able to locate in their private caches.

2.3 Cache coherency protocol

2.3.1 MESIF protocol. Cache coherency in the Intel Xeon Scalable processor architecture is implemented using the MESIF protocol [8], with transitions among the following states: *modified* (M), *exclusive* (E), *shared* (S), *invalid* (I), and *forward* (F).

2.3.2 Snoop Filter. Given the shift from an inclusive to a non-inclusive cache hierarchy, in processors of the Intel Xeon Scalable family, a new structure is required for tracking the cache lines

inside the processor – the *snoop filter* [16]. The snoop filter acts as a socket-level directory, keeping track of all cache lines that are present in the private L1 and L2 caches but not in the LLC. The snoop filter is inclusive of the private L1 and L2 caches; therefore, evictions of snoop filter entries (e.g. due to insufficient capacity), are handled by evicting the corresponding cache lines from all private caches [27, 39]. Given these characteristics, the snoop filter resembles the sparse directories discussed in [10].

2.3.3 Directory-based Coherency. For tracking cache lines across multiple sockets, the Intel Xeon Scalable processor architecture and the UPI interconnect implement a directory-based home-snoop coherency protocol [16]. It is based on an in-memory directory structure, which utilizes extra bits alongside each cache line, that indicate its caching status in foreign memory domains. Specifically, three states are possible for each line: invalid (I), which indicates that the line is *not* cached in any other socket; snoopAll (A), which hints that the data *may be* cached in a foreign socket, including in the exclusive (E) or modified (M) states; and shared (S), which specifies that the line may be present in another socket, but not in an *exclusive* manner, and thus the data inside the memory is valid.

2.3.4 HitME cache. Accessing the directory for retrieving information about sockets that hold a copy of a cache line is costly due to its DRAM residency. Already since processors generations predating the Xeon Scalable family, Intel has introduced an optimization called the HitME (Hit-M/E) cache [14, 29]. The HitME structure acts like a cache for the in-memory directory, storing information about the presence of cache lines in remote sockets. Specifically, the HitME cache tracks cache lines that reside in remote caching agents in the modified (M), or, exclusive (E) states. Hits in the HitME cache save directory look-up and allow for prompt cross-socket snoops.

2.3.5 Opportunistic Snoop Broadcast. A final optimization in the Intel Xeon Scalable processor line-up, inherited from previous generations, is the Opportunistic Snoop Broadcast (OSB) mechanism [22]. With OSB, the CHA is able to speculatively generate cross-socket snoops, while it’s still waiting on the costly directory lookup to complete. If the directory lookup indicates that a snoop was indeed required, the CHA waits on a response to the already sent snoop; otherwise, the snoop and its imminent response are simply disregarded. The opportunistic snoop might be issued only under specific preconditions, such as non-heavily loaded UPI links.

3 PERFORMANCE ANOMALY

In this section, we analyze the performance anomaly observed in the shared-memory broadcast algorithm, on multi-socket nodes of the Intel Xeon Scalable processor architecture. We examine how the different cache coherency mechanisms on these systems interact with each other, in the context of shared-memory communication. Finally, we highlight the anomaly for the case of the broadcast implementation presented in Section 2.1, describing its cause and the impact of the cache coherency scheme.

3.1 Cache coherency scheme

In Section 2.3, we provided an overview of components involved in the cache coherence scheme for Intel Xeon Scalable processors. Different mechanisms handle coherency at different levels of the

processor stack, and each of them has its own discrete effect on performance. We dissect the cache coherency scheme in these processors, in the context of the broadcast algorithm. For the discussion and analysis that follows, we assume that the root rank has previously written the cache lines containing the data to be broadcast. Consequently, the cache lines comprising the data exist in the private cache of the core on which the root is pinned, in the modified (M) state of the MESIF protocol. For simplicity, in the scenarios that follow, we assume that, just a single cache line of data is broadcast. The process generally repeats in similar fashion for the rest of the cache lines. Note that, each process is pinned to one specific core, exclusively. Therefore, the terms core and process, will be used interchangeably hereafter. The figures in this section show an abstracted view of the internal mesh interconnect and other components important for the analysis – the actual count, type, and arrangement of tiles will differ in actual processors.

Official in-depth information from Intel on these systems is not publicly available. The findings in this section are the result of investigative research work combining multiple sources, including the description of the MESIF protocol, published patents, and other online documentation & manuals, augmented by our own verification and analysis using hardware performance monitoring counters. The investigation is focused on the newest architecture, Ice Lake, and unless otherwise stated, the protocol analysis refers to it. However, in high-level view, the general scheme described is applicable for all three generations of Intel Xeon Scalable processors. Note that some of the low-level details may be different on other systems, depending on BIOS configuration, hardware layout, or other factors. Furthermore, it’s possible that the internal protocol might exhibit functional differences according to dynamic conditions (e.g. system load, power state, cache occupancy, interconnect utilization).

For the experimental investigation, we rely on our own purpose-built software [21]. This tool offers an intuitive way to prepare and simulate a desired communication pattern in fine-grain manner. It monitors & captures performance counter events that occur during its execution, and measures the latency of each contained operation (e.g. read, write). For the scenarios outlined in this section, we mark for each step the key performance counter events [17] that hint at the occurrence of the behaviour that we describe. The coherency state transitions discussed below cannot be fully deduced through performance counters; for these results, we also rely on the latency measurements. This is done by observing the amount of time required for various operations, after a core has acquired a cache line. For example, a write operation will be quick if the cache line was acquired in the exclusive (E) or in the modified (M) state. On the other hand, it will be slower, if it was acquired in the shared (S) or forward (F) state.

Single-socket. In the single-socket scenario, only local ranks, i.e. ranks that reside in the same socket as the root process, access the root’s (RT) data. Initially, we focus on the first, in terms of time, reader to access RT’s cache lines(s). This reader is henceforth referred to as R1. Figure 3 shows the different steps that will take place in order to fulfill R1’s access. To begin with, as soon as root sets the synchronization flag, R1 issues a *load* instruction for the cache line. The core searches for the line in the private L1/L2 caches

Table 2: MESIF state of obtained cache lines

Scenario	Skylake	Cascade Lake	Ice Lake
Local read	Shared (S/F)	Shared (S/F)	Exclusive (E)
Remote read	Exclusive (E)	Exclusive (E)	Exclusive (E)
Remote read, after local read	Exclusive (E)	Exclusive (E)	Shared (S/F)
Local read, after remote read	Exclusive (E)	Exclusive (E)	Shared (S/F)

(step 1), but misses¹. Thus, the next move is to send the request to the CHA that is responsible for the specific line (CHx) (step 2)². Note that the CHA responsible for any cache line is determined according to the line’s physical address [28]. CHx looks up the line in the co-located last-level cache (LLC) slice and snoop filter (SF) (step 3). The SF look-up results in a hit³, as the line is cached in RT’s L1/L2. The CHA snoops⁴ RT, who responds⁵ with the requested line (step 4). Finally, CHx responds to R1 with the requested cache line (step 5). The MESIF state in which R1 will take the line varies across different architecture generations. This information is presented in Table 2. The first row corresponds to the specific scenario discussed, while the different columns depict the state of the cache line, for each of the three explored architectures. As this table shows, on Ice Lake, R1 acquires the line in the exclusive (E) state; thus the cache line is invalidated from RT’s private caches. However as we’ve observed on Ice Lake, the line is not written-back to memory in this instance, even though R1 has it in the exclusive (E), and not in the modified (M) state. Instead, the line is *also* allocated in the LLC, in the modified (M) state. This is a practical example of the mostly-non-inclusive LLC of the Intel Xeon Scalable processor architecture behaving in an inclusive manner. Information around the non-inclusive LLC, the distributed snoop filter, and inclusiveness with private L1/L2 caches may be found in [31]. This functionality also resembles the weak-exclusive cache hierarchies discussed in [19].

Figure 3: Cache coherency for 1st local read of shared data

Further on, we examine the operation of the protocol when a second reader (R2) issues a load for the data. This is depicted in

¹CORE.L2_RQSTS.DEMAND_DATA_RD_MISS²CORE.OFFCORE_REQUESTS.DEMAND_DATA_RD³CHA.LLC_LOOKUP.SF_E⁴CHA.CORE_SNP.CORE_ONE⁵CORE.CORE_SNOOP_RESPONSE.I_FWD_M

Figure 4. R2 initially looks up its private L1/L2 cache for the line (step 1), and misses. Thus, he requests the line from the associated CHA (CHx) (step 2). CHx checks the LLC and SF for the line (step 3), and it discovers it in the LLC⁶, in the modified (M) state. But, there’s also information that it’s present in R1’s private cache, in the exclusive (E) state. In order for CHx to determine that the copy of the line in the LLC is valid, and R1 hasn’t modified it, it snoops R1 (step 4). R1 receives the snoop, and responds⁷ to CHx (step 5) that the data *is not* modified. Therefore, CHx uses the value from the LLC to respond to R2’s original request (step 6) for the cache line. R1’s copy remains in its cache, but it transitions to the shared (S) state, and R2 also caches the line in the shared (S) state. The line does remain in the LLC in the modified (M) state.

Figure 4: Cache coherency for 2nd local read of shared data

Finally, for the rest of the readers, the behaviour is identical. Let us assume a reader Rn, who accesses the cache line 3rd or later in order. Rn will miss in the private L1/L2, and thus will request the line from the CHA (CHx). The CHA will look up the line in the LLC and SF, and will locate it in the LLC in the modified (M) state. This time around, the line is already shared between two or more cores, so there can’t be any dirty data in any private cache. Therefore, the data in the LLC is valid, and no cross-core snoops are necessary⁸. The CHA responds to Rn’s request using the data from the LLC. Rn will obtain and cache the line in the shared (S) state.

Multi-socket. In the multi-socket scenarios, we also populate the second socket with processes. Similarly to the single socket scenarios, the data to be broadcast are in the modified (M) state in the root’s private cache. Initially, a remote reader (Rr) accesses the shared data, and is the first reader in any socket to do so. The steps for this access are shown in Figure 5. To begin with, Rr misses in its private L1/L2 (step 1), so he needs to send the request to the designated CHA. In the dual-socket scenario, essentially, two CHAs in total, are of interest for each cache line. The first is the CHA in the *home socket* (CHx), i.e. the socket on whose attached memory the line is allocated; CHx handles caching inside the socket, as well as memory operations for the line. The second one is the CHA in the remote socket (CHy), which only handles caching inside the remote socket. Rr sends the request to the CHA in the same socket as him – CHy (step 2). CHy checks the SF and LLC (step 3) for the presence of the cache line in this socket, but misses⁹. CHy

⁶CHA.LLC_LOOKUP.M⁷CORE.CORE_SNOOP_RESPONSE.S_HIT_FSE⁸MEM_LOAD_L3_HIT_RETIRED.XSNP_NONE⁹CHA.LLC_LOOKUP.I

knows through the line’s address that it is remotely homed (i.e. it is allocated in foreign socket’s memory). Therefore, through the UPI interconnect, it requests¹⁰ a copy of the line from the designated CHA in the home socket (CHx) (step 4). CHx looks up the line in the local LLC and SF (step 5), and hits in the SF. Similarly to the single-socket scenario, CHx will snoop¹¹ RT, who will accordingly respond with the data (step not visible here). At this point, CHx sends the line to CHy (step 8), but some extra steps also take place in the local socket: (1) the dirty data is written back to memory, (2) the in-memory directory is set¹² to the snoopAll (A) state (step 7), to indicate that the data is cached in a remote socket, and optionally (3) a new entry tracking the line’s location is allocated in the local HitME cache structure. CHy receives the cache line, and responds to Rr’s original request for it (step 9). At the end of this scenario the line is in Rr’s private caches, in the exclusive (E) state. Table 2 (row 2) shows the state across all three architectures.

Figure 5: Cache coherency for 1st remote read (shared data)

In an alternative scenario where a local reader had already obtained the cache line before the remote reader’s (Rr) access, the flow of the coherency protocol remains similar. The line would be located in the local reader’s private cache, instead of RT’s, as well as in the LLC in modified (M) state, as described in the respective single-socket scenario. The home CHA would snoop this core, to verify the copy in the LLC is not stale, and would then respond to the remote CHA (CHy) with the data. However, the coherency state in which Rr would take the line might differ, depending on the architecture generation; this state is shown in the 3rd row of Table 2.

The final scenario describes the protocol when a local reader attempts to access the line, after a remote reader has taken it in the exclusive (E) state, like it happens in the first multi-socket scenario examined above. The steps that take place as a result of the local reader’s (Rl) access are shown in Figure 6. Rl looks up the line in its L1/L2 (step 1) and misses, so he requests the line from the designated CHA (CHx) (step 2). CHx looks up the LLC and SF (step 3). At this point, the behaviour differentiates slightly, depending on the availability of opportunistic snoop broadcast (OSB), and whether there is an entry for the line in the HitME cache. Assuming initially that there isn’t an entry in the HitME\$, CHx misses in the LLC and SF, so it fetches the cache line from memory (step 4). This

also retrieves the state of the line in the in-memory directory¹³. The state is snoopAll (A), therefore CHx *has to snoop*¹⁴ the remote socket (step 5) for the line. If instead there was an entry in the HitME cache¹⁵, it would immediately be known that the line is cached in the remote socket, and the directory lookup would not have taken place. Furthermore, if OSB is supported and the system conditions allowed it, the snoop will have already been sent¹⁶ speculatively while waiting for the directory information to arrive from memory. The cross-socket snoop is directed to the designated CHA in the remote socket for this line (CHy). CHy looks up the LLC and SF (step 6). The line is currently cached in Rr’s L1/L2, and this is reflected in the SF, so CHy snoops Rr, and Rr responds with the data (not shown here). CHy responds¹⁷ to CHx (step 8), and CHx responds to Rl’s request for the line (not shown here). Additionally, CHx performs a write to memory, in order to update¹⁸ the state of the line in the directory to shared (S) one (step 9). At the end of the scenario, on Ice Lake, the line is cached in both Rr and Rl, in the shared (S) state. However, as shown in the 4th row of Table 2, on Skylake and Cascade Lake the line is *again* acquired by the local reader in the exclusive (E) state. We’ve observed that on these architectures, the state stabilizes to the shared (S) one after about 2 readers from each socket have accessed the line.

Figure 6: Cache coherency for local read of shared data, after remote one

3.2 Phenomenon analysis

In order to investigate the observed anomaly, we evaluate and analyze the performance of the shared-memory broadcast for different scenarios of participating processes. These scenarios cover cases of different node occupancies, including ones with multiple sockets. The test systems are the ones listed in Table 1.

Figure 7 plots the latency of the broadcast operation, for multiple message sizes and different node occupancy ratios. The horizontal axis shows the number of total active ranks. The ranks are mapped sequentially in regards to cores and sockets in the system. Therefore, up until 12 or 24 total ranks, on SKX-24 and CSX-48/ICX-48 respectively, only a single socket is active. Past this point, the first socket is fully populated, and the number of active ranks on the

¹⁰CHA.TOR_INSERTS.RRQRD_DATA

¹¹CHA.CORE_SNP.REMOTE_ONE

¹²CHA.DIR_UPDATE.TOR

¹³CHA.DIR_LOOKUP

¹⁴CHA.SNOOPS_SENT.CHA.TOR_INSERTS.IPQ.SNP_DATA

¹⁵CHA.LLC_LOOKUP.SF_H.CHA.HITME_HIT.EX_RDS

¹⁶CHA.OSB.LOCAL_READ

¹⁷CHA.SNOOP_RESP.RSP_S_FWD

¹⁸DIR_UPDATE.HA

Figure 7: Average latency of readers, grouped by locality, as node occupancy increases

second increases. Instead of the average latency of all ranks, this plot groups the ranks according to their locality (*local* to root, i.e. in the same socket, or *remote*), and shows the average latency of each group. The root (rank 0) resides in the first socket. The performance degradation appears at the point where the second socket starts getting populated. Until this point, the average latency of local ranks steadily increases, as a result of internal congestion from the increasing data copies. When remote readers are added, no change to the number of active ranks in the first socket occurs; but, we notice a distinct and severe elevation in the average latency of *local* ranks, for almost all message sizes. Generally, the presence of additional readers, even if those reside in a remote socket, is expected to impact the performance of the local socket, as they do draw data from it. However, the magnitude of this increase is not justified, and the rise is instead attributed to another factor.

The effect is linked to the cache coherency protocol, and the decisions it assumes. Recall the operation of the cache coherency protocol in scenarios involving multiple sockets from Section 3.1, and Table 2, which shows the MESIF state in which readers obtain cache lines in various scenarios. On Ice Lake, if the first reader to access the root’s data is a remote one, he obtains the cache line in the exclusive (E) state. On Skylake and Cascade Lake, the first of the remote readers to access the data obtains them in exclusive (E) state (even if a local reader accessed it earlier). When a line gets cached in a socket exclusively, the data is invalidated from all other sockets. As a result, any local readers that subsequently attempt to obtain it, can no longer do so from the local cache hierarchy, which they were always able to do (for messages that fit in the cache) in the single-socket scenario. Instead, in this case, the designated CHA has to snoop the remote socket in order to obtain the cache line, which is considerably more expensive than a local shared cache access. Indicatively, on the systems studied in this work, a local (core-to-core) read of one cache line takes 65~75 ns, while one that misses locally and has to wait for the remote socket to be snooped, ~250 ns on SKX-24/CSX-48 and ~150 ns on ICX-48. The problem is further exacerbated if the cache line is not present in the HitME cache, and OSB is unavailable. Note that OSB is not supported on Skylake and Cascade Lake for data reads [16], while on Ice Lake it is expected to be dynamically disabled when the UPI links are congested. In such a case, the latency of the (supposedly) local operation(s) will be even higher, as the snoop will be deferred until the directory state has arrived from the main memory.

We also observe that the rise in the average latency of local ranks is the highest when just one remote reader is present, whereas it becomes slightly less pronounced with two or more readers. We believe this to be attributed to the location of the cache lines in the remote socket. The first remote reader will obtain the cache lines and store them in its private cache. If a second remote reader exists, he will obtain the lines from the first one, through cross-core snoops by the CHA, but the lines will subsequently also get placed in the LLC in the remote socket, similarly to the respective scenarios in Section 3.1. As a result, the incoming cross-socket snoop for the line is serviced faster when the CHA in the remote socket finds the line in the LLC, versus when it has to snoop a core, making the effect less intense when more than one remote readers are present. Finally, note that the release flag used to signal the beginning of the shared-memory broadcast, also exhibits a similar communication pattern to the actual data transmission. Therefore, the accesses to this cache line are also susceptible to the phenomenon, and further influence the overall broadcast latency.

All these factors contribute towards abnormally elevated latency for local reads in the multi-socket scenario. Figure 8 plots the slow-down in the performance of local ranks, with 2 vs 1 fully populated sockets. The phenomenon is significantly more pronounced on SKX-24 and CSX-48, versus ICX-48, reaching slowdowns upwards of 4.5 \times in small messages and up to 2 \times on large ones. This is due to differences in protocol state transitions, affecting the combination of on-chip and off-chip (cross-socket) lookups. Additionally, the lack of OSB for data reads on the former architecture generations, potentially also contributes to the difference. On ICX-48 the slow-down is of the scale of 2 \times for small messages, but only marginal for large ones. On Ice Lake if only a single reader from the local socket obtains the cache line before any remote ones, the effect is not triggered. Thus the chance for the phenomenon to occur is significantly reduced, resulting in smaller performance degradation.

4 RECTIFICATION APPROACHES

We cannot alter, or control, the hardware-based cache coherency protocol, in a way that would completely prevent the adverse performance effect observed. However, we introduce software-based techniques to mitigate its impact, albeit not without their own trade-offs. We provide proof-of-concept modifications to the shared-memory broadcast algorithm, discuss the applicability of each approach, and evaluate their impact on the performance of broadcast.

Figure 8: Increase in average latency of root-local ranks, with the 2nd socket fully occupied

4.1 Ordering accesses

The first group of techniques is based on ordering accesses of processes on different sockets. We refer to processes located on the same socket as the root rank, as *local* ones, while processes on other sockets are referred to as *remote* ones. The main idea is to allow local processes to fetch the requested cache lines, *before* any remote processes start accessing them. To this end, we explore various techniques to introduce a degree of delay for remote processes.

The first one is to have local and remote processes synchronize by means of shared memory resident flags. Each local rank divides the broadcast message in chunks. As soon as a chunk is copied, the rank sets a shared memory flag to notify remote processes of it. Remote processes poll all these shared flags and, when at least one of them is set, they proceed to copy the chunk. The drawback to this approach is that local and remote processes pass through several synchronization points before completing the message transfer. Although the technique does provide strong guarantees for the desired ordering, it also introduces notable overhead. We also examine a relaxed version of this technique, with synchronization for only the first chunk of the message. This variant assumes that once local ranks are ahead of remote ones by just a single chunk, then the rest of the message will be accessed in the appropriate order.

Another approach relies on artificially delaying remote readers through a short busy-wait loop. This interval can be as short as a few micro-seconds. Although this technique is more straightforward to implement, it’s not guaranteed to be fully effective. It is susceptible to system noise, and relies on the assumption of no late or early process arrivals. For example, if local processes encounter a minor delay in joining the broadcast, comparable to the injected artificial delay, the approach will be ineffective. Similarly, if remote ranks join late in relation to local ones, the applied delay will be redundant.

Finally, it should be noted that these approaches are only meaningful for messages of moderate or larger size. Figure 9 presents the improvement through this approach in the overall MPI broadcast performance, with the fully robust flag-based technique (delay-flag-strict), and the relaxed flag-based one (delay-flag), compared to the baseline implementation. The showcased systems are CSX-48 and ICX-48, and the configured chunk size on them is 16K and 2K, respectively. Let us note that, a limited empirical exploration for different chunk size values has shown that these two values achieve the best performance. A more rigorous method for deriving optimal chunk sizes is out of current study’s scope. On CSX-48, the

technique successfully mitigates the phenomenon, and the relaxed variant reduces the latency of the broadcast operation by up to 1.2 \times , compared to the baseline. As discussed in Section 3.2, on ICX-48 and with large messages, the phenomenon is much less severe, so the observed benefit from this technique is marginal, if any. The strict variant achieves a small benefit on CSX-48, but notably smaller than the relaxed one. On ICX-48, where the benefit from it is marginal, its cost results in significant performance loss.

Figure 9: Delay-based performance remedy

4.2 Separate buffers

A second approach, intended for smaller messages and shared-memory-segment communication, involves using different shared buffers and synchronization structures for local (relative to root) and remote readers. In the original broadcast implementation, all readers poll the same shared synchronization flag and they all retrieve the data from the same shared buffer, which constitutes breeding ground for the phenomenon. Instead, according to this technique, we allocate multiple shared buffers and synchronization flags (e.g. one for local readers, one for remote ones). The root rank copies the data into all of the buffers, and sets the different synchronization flags. Following this method, readers in different sockets now access completely different synchronization flags and data buffers. This effectively eliminates the conflict between them and completely avoids the studied phenomenon. The updated algorithm incorporating this technique is illustrated in Figure 10; this figure is a juxtaposition of Figure 2, in Section 2.1. The drawback to this technique is that the root has to perform more copies into shared buffers and set more flags. Moreover, it increases the time readers have to wait before they begin copying out the data. As the message size increases, the cost of extra copies rises. For this reason, this technique is not cost-effective for large messages.

Figure 10: Shared-memory broadcast with multiple buffers and synchronization flags

In Figure 11, we evaluate the performance of this approach (*dual buffer*), compared to the original implementation (baseline). The applied approach includes both multiple data buffers and multiple synchronization flags. The multiple data buffers are only enabled for the copy-in-copy-out transport mode, which is active for all messages of 512 bytes or less. This technique reduces the latency of the small-messages broadcast, by up to $1.7\times$ and $1.5\times$, on SKX-24 and ICX-48, respectively.

Figure 11: Dual-buffer-based performance remedy

4.3 Special instructions

Finally, an alternative approach is to use special instructions of the x86 architecture that can indirectly influence the coherency state of cache lines. Specifically, we developed a software remedy based on the CLWB (Cache Line Write-Back) instruction. CLWB requests that any dirty data of a cache line be written back to memory. But unlike similar instructions (CLFLUSH, CLFLUSHOPT), it hints that the clean line should remain in the cache hierarchy. The behaviour of CLWB is different on Ice Lake, compared to Skylake or Cascade Lake; on the latter architectures, it does not actually keep the line in the cache hierarchy. Thus, this technique and our analysis in this section only focuses on ICX-48.

CLWB may be utilized at the beginning of the broadcast operation. It is beneficial in the scenario that the root has recently written the data to be broadcast, and therefore has the cache lines comprising the data buffer in its private cache(s), in the modified (M) state. Note that this will always be the case for the internal shared buffer, in the copy-in-copy-out scenario. At this point, executing the CLWB instruction (for all the cache lines in the message), causes the dirty data to be written back, while the clean cache lines are kept in the LLC, in the exclusive (E) state. Thus, the lines are taken by remote readers in the shared (S) state, even if they access them before any local ones do. In effect, the lines remain in the cache hierarchy of the local socket during the entire operation, preventing performance degradation. Figure 12 shows the performance improvement through the CLWB-based rectification technique, in comparison to the baseline broadcast. In this implementation, the root rank issues the CLWB instruction for all cache lines in the data buffer before setting the synchronization flag. The overall broadcast latency is reduced, though not by much, reaching a factor of 2–5%.

Figure 12: Clwb-based performance remedy (ICX-48)

5 OPTIMIZED SHARED-MEMORY BROADCAST

Finally, we capitalize on our analysis and findings regarding techniques that mitigate the phenomenon triggering the performance anomaly. We combine the most efficient of the considered techniques, and produce an optimized cache-coherency-aware version of the shared-memory broadcast. Specifically, we utilize the *delay-flag* (relaxed variant) and the *dual-buffer* approaches outlined in Sections 4.1 and 4.2, respectively.

For small messages, up to 512 bytes in size, where the copy-in-copy-out transport is active, multiple shared buffers are utilized. Furthermore, different synchronization flags are used to release ranks in different sockets. The latter is useful for all message sizes, and thus is always enabled. In large messages, the delay-based technique is activated; the configured chunk size is 4 KB and 8 KB, on SKX-24 and CSX-48, respectively. On Ice Lake, the benefit of this technique is marginal, so it’s always disabled for ICX-48.

Figure 13 shows the performance of the optimized cache-coherency-aware shared-memory broadcast, compared to the baseline implementation, on all three systems examined. Furthermore, Figure 14 plots the achieved speedup across all message sizes on all hosts. We reduce broadcast latency for small messages by $1.4–1.6\times$ across all systems, while we improve the performance of large message broadcast by up to $1.15–1.25\times$ on SKX-24 and CSX-48. Unfortunately, on SKX-24 and CSX-48, there is a minor performance drop, for a limited number of medium message sizes. None of our techniques are activated in this range, while some necessary modifications that are in place for other message sizes cannot be *fully* turned off. Thus, there is a slight penalty in this message range, with no applied technique to offset it. The solution would be to disable the aforementioned modifications for certain message sizes, but the original framework currently lacks the appropriate infrastructure.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We have demonstrated a particularly challenging performance degradation scenario in the case of shared-memory-based MPI broadcast, on three generations of the Intel Xeon Scalable processor architecture. Based on analysis of hardware-based performance counters, we conclude that the performance degradation observed is attributed to the cache coherency protocol and the multi-socket configuration of the execution platforms examined. We expect the performance anomaly analyzed in this work to be relevant for other

Figure 13: Overall performance with selected remedies

Figure 14: Speedup with selected remedies

multi-socket platforms where processes of a remote socket can acquire a cache line in the exclusive state. Affected architectures may include both Intel and AMD systems, with MESI-, MESIF-, or MOESI-like coherency protocols. It is not feasible to alter or control the hardware-based cache coherency protocol in a way that would completely prevent the adverse performance effect observed. However, we have introduced software-based techniques to mitigate its impact, which we apply in a cache coherency aware version of the MPI broadcast implementation. We improve the overall latency of the broadcast operation by up to 1.5 \times and 1.25 \times for small and large messages, respectively.

We have discussed how the order in which processes initiate requests affects the performance anomaly identified. In current work, we explore how different implementations for the barrier operation in the OSU micro-benchmark, which synchronizes the ranks as they enter the broadcast operation, affect the phenomenon’s presence and intensity. Moreover, for the case of large messages we expect snoop filter evictions to come into play, with the resulting performance impacted by the mixed effect of evictions and cache line migration. In future work, we aim to extend our analysis to more complex inter-process communication patterns, including hierarchical algorithms for MPI collectives. Finally, of special interest is the investigation and quantification of similar performance anomalies on other platforms.

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